
Relationship of Parental Exemplary with Christian Character: A Literature Review

Rida Gultom¹, Binur Panjaitan², Junjungan Simorangkir³

Article history:

Received: March, 05, 2023; Accepted: May 05, 2023; Displayed Online: May 11, 2023; Published: June 30, 2023

Keywords

Obedience;

Parent;

Character;

Christian;

Abstract

The research aims to determine how much the contribution of applying the example of parents to students' Christian character is. The method used is the method of literature research. The research subjects were students and parents. Data collection techniques are observation and documentation. The results of this study understand that there is a relationship between parental example and children's character, namely that parental example is very much needed at the stage of student development because students imitate the good attitudes and behavior of people from their surroundings coupled with strengthening 'emotional bonding' between children and parents, efforts to infiltrate values -moral values and good character in children will be easier to do.

1. Introduction

Human character is determined by the mentality possessed. If the mentality is good, then the character will also be good. However, if the mentality is bad, the character will also be bad, as in various phenomena among teenagers or students in uncomfortable situations or a moral crisis. It is not only happening in urban areas but has occurred in rural areas. As a phenomenon that has happened before, namely in Sidikalang Middle School- Indonesia, students got into fights due to mutual mockery between students, which led to death and entangling in legal cases (Tim-Kompas, 2020). Apart from that, there was a fight between students at SMP N 2 Sipoholon, which had to be reconciled at the police station. Students whom adults influence take part in stealing other people's things.

¹ Institut Agama Kristen Negeri, Tarutung, Indonesia, Email: ridagultom@gmail.com

² Institut Agama Kristen Negeri, Tarutung, Indonesia, Email: panjaitan_binur@yahoo.com

³ Institut Agama Kristen Negeri, Tarutung, Indonesia, Email: jsimorangkir271@gmail.com

It is necessary to involve and play the role of parents in supervising children (students) when they are with their families, namely through the example of parents giving rules and discipline every day. In this case, parents become role models, role models and priests for their children, which is reflected in the attitudes, daily actions, and spirituality of parents as in Deuteronomy 6: 6-7: What I command you today you must pay attention to, you must teach it to repeat to your children and talk about it when you sit in your house, when you are on your way, when you lie down and when you get up; 1 Thessalonians 5:14b, rebuke those who live disorderly; Proverbs 22: 6: Educate young people according to the way they deserve; Ephesians 6: 4 Educate them in God's teachings and advice.

Parents are responsible for shaping the character of children. Because parents are children's first teachers (Sarumpaet, 1995), Christian parents must realize that the family is the center of the formation of children's character (Harefa, 2016). The family is a place to give energy, attention, commitment, and love, and an environment conducive to growing toward Christ Jesus (Antoni, 2010). Parental example is very influential in the formation of students' Christian character. Parents, as God's mandate, must play a role and be responsible for the formation of the character of students as a millennial generation so that they have compassion, empathy, self-mastery, respect, tolerance, fairness, and love for the motherland.

The results of Jeti et al. concluded that the family has an important role in instilling these values as the basis for character education through habituation and example from an early age in everyday life, namely by getting used to and modeling the behavior of mutual love and respect for each other, mutual respect, mutual protect, cooperate and empathize (Jeti, L., Manan, Risman, K., 2021). The application of Christian character values can shape children into individuals with character.

Parents' good relationship has a relationship with children's character. Rohner in Wibowo said that a person's childhood experience greatly influences the development of his later personality, including his character or emotional intelligence (Wibowo, 2017). Parental example is the most important part of shaping the character of children.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper is based on descriptive qualitative research, namely library research or literature studies, to analyze writings written by Christian theology experts, Christian Religious Education experts, and learning experts. Literature can be in the form of books and journal articles relevant to the discussion in writing. It aims to explain how the relationship between parental example and Christian character. Based on the opinions of these experts, the researcher will combine the opinions of these experts with the opinions of the researchers through the results of reading the researchers and elaborating them with various relevant sources and then presenting them descriptively so that a new view is obtained that is useful for providing solutions to the problems being studied.

3. Results and Discussions

Students have a sinful nature, so students can make mistakes at any time. The consequence of sin is the breakdown of human relationships with God, others, and even oneself. The sinful nature of students makes them act inappropriately according to the right thing, meaning that doing something is not following its function (Kadarmanto, 2016). Students need people who direct them to the right path (Brummelen, 2006). Every human being is given free will, including students. Free will means that humans have the will to do what they want within the limits of their ability.

The intended freedom is to do what is right and what is evil (Deut. 20:19). The Westminster Confession of Faith says that "the will cannot depart from the moral character from which it

originates" (G.I. Williamson, 2017). If a person's character is not good, they will be carried out tends to deviate and lead to evil.

Everyone has a different character; a person's character will affect how he behaves in everyday life. Technological advances and lifestyle developments will slowly change a child's character if no one controls or directs the child. Good character will develop good behavior; through the formation of good character, students will be able to distinguish good from bad so that students can decide on every action.

The number of problems that are increasingly endangering the nation's life is one reason for the importance of forming student character from an early age (Kadarwati, 2013). So, in this case, the student character formation referred to by the author is by teaching and applying Christian character to students through the example of parents.

Christian character

Character is "innate, heart, soul, personality, character, behavior, personality, nature, character, temperament, character" (Ministry of National Education, 2010). Character comes from the Greek language, which means "to mark" or to mark and focus on how to apply good values in the form of action or behavior so that people who are dishonest, cruel, greedy, and other bad behaviors are said to have bad character. Conversely, a person whose behavior is following moral rules is called a noble character.

In the General Indonesian Dictionary, the character is written as "character, temperament, and characteristics of a person. Character is defined as having a personality, while personality is defined as a person's unique and essential nature that distinguishes a person from others (Zain, 1996). "Children's character consists of healthy and unhealthy characters. A child who has a healthy character does not mean that he has never done negative things but that these actions are still in the normal category. However, children with unhealthy characters have behavior that deviates from existing norms.

Characters that belong to the healthy category include: (1) high affiliation, that is, it is easy to accept other people as friends, very tolerant of other people and can be invited to work together, has many friends, and is liked by his friends; (2) high power, namely controlling his friends but with a positive attitude, being able to lead his friends, being able to take his initiative, so that he can be a role model for others; (3) an achiever, who is always motivated to achieve (achievement oriented), puts himself ahead of others (egocentric); (4) asserter, that is straightforward, assertive, and does not talk much, has a good balance between own interests and the interests of others, easily accepted by the environment; (5) adventurer, who likes adventure, although not always going to nature but prefers trying new things.

Thus, the character is a person's personality that distinguishes it from others. Gede Raka also gave almost the same view: "In general, the character is associated with special or special traits, moral strength, or a person's pattern of behavior." From the above understanding, it can be concluded that character can be expressed as a person's nature in character, character, and personal behavior that can shape one's personality.

Character is what and who we are, whether others see us or not. There are all kinds of characters: physical, emotional, intellectual. However, this is not what is meant here; the main thing is the moral character (moral character). Maybe, a good practice if we imagine what people will say at our funeral. They will say not about titles or possessions but our character, that we are generous and helpful, or people will say we are stingy (Gill, 2000).

The word "character" in English comes from the Greek *charassein*, which means "to engrave, to carve," as in wax tablets, gemstones, or metal surfaces. From this root word, the meaning of character

develops as a special sign or guide, and from there grows the conception that character is "an individual's behavior pattern... that is, his moral state. Everyone is marked by negativity, patience, indolence, concern, kindness, and the like. Nevertheless, according to Ryan and Bohlin, a fixed character – for example, a good character – goes far beyond just a fixed pattern of behavior and behavior. Good character is about "knowing what is good, loving what is good, and doing what is good" (Gill, 2000).

The three are closely related. We are born with a self-centered, ignorant orientation in which our primitive drives dominate our reasoning. All educational and upbringing efforts are to bring inclinations, feelings, and ideals in harmony with reason. Knowing good includes arriving at an understanding of good and evil. It means developing the ability to assess situations and consciously choose the right thing to do and do it. It is what Aristotle called practical reason.

Character, as defined above, describes the formation of positive or good character. Contrary to the positive, there are also negative characteristics. Even this character is formed in a person because of the environment. For example, a person who behaves dishonestly, cheats, is cruel and greedy is said to have a bad character, whereas a person who behaves well, is honest, and helpful is called a person who has good character.

Character is the provision of students to deal with global culture and multidimensional crises that are very popular now. Of course, the definitions of character above seem very complex, but the question that needs to be answered is, what is good character? Is good character related to religion, especially Christianity? The author agrees to link the characteristics of good character with the rules of religion or the Christian faith. In other words, virtue characterizes a person's character because it comes from one's faith (religion) beliefs. In a Christian view, a good or positive value cannot conflict with the contents of God's Word in the Bible. So, it can be concluded that character in a Christian view is living our lives before God, fearing only God, and trying only to please God, no matter how we feel or what other people might say or do.

From a Christian perspective, the character can be used as a brief statement that functions as a guide for action that determines what is right to do (or vice versa, what not to do). The principles are broad, general, and inclusive – like what is often called the golden rule "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you" (just as you like others to do to you, do it to others, says Jesus) (Gill, 2000) (cf. Luke 6:31). Another example is the "principle of utility," namely "Do what results in the greatest happiness for the greatest number" (Gill, 2000).

Christian character is a process, method, or deed forming innate heart, soul, personality, character, behavior, personality, one's character, temperament character. To apply the value of goodness in the form of action or behavior and have the personality, characteristics, and essentials of a follower of Christ, like Christ, have the status of a Christian, and show faith as a follower of Christians.

The characteristics of a Christian perspective by Sugiyanto are as follows: Godly character (Father-Child), loving character, giving character, caring character, giving is nobler than receiving, not easily offended and non-violent, humble and happy, friendly, disciplined and responsible, gender equality, with a national perspective (Suyanto, 2022). Sidjaga added the values of Christian character, namely: "Trustworthy, respectful, responsible, fair, caring, societal, honesty, courage, diligent, and integrity" (Sitanding, 1994). Lidya Indriswari stated the characteristics of Christian students: caring, humble, honest, responsible, and fair (Indriswari & Giawa, 2020).

Christian Character Values and Student Indicators with Christian Character

Gunawan's opinion that Christian character values that are developed are: integrity (Titus 1:7-9), humility (Matthew 5:1-7; Mark 10:14-15; 1 Timothy 3:6), love with all its characteristics (Matthew 22:37-39), serving and helping (Luke 10:25-37), inner strength and truth (Luke 11:37-53; John 16:33), a close relationship with Christ (1 Timothy 6:11; John 15:1-8), joy (John 17:13), holiness (John 17:16), peace (2 Timothy 2:22), patience and perseverance (1 Timothy 6:11; 2 Timothy 3:10), gentle (1 Timothy 6:11), self-control (1 Timothy 3:2; Titus 1:8), not greedy and not contentious (1 Timothy 3:2-3), as well as other character qualities in 2 Peter 1: 5-8 such as virtue, knowledge, perseverance, and piety (Gunawan, 2013).

Nuhamara explained that one example of the value of Christian character is as an embodiment of the fruit of the Spirit in Galatians 5:22-23, as follows: "But the fruit of the Spirit is love, joy, peace, patience, kindness, kindness, faithfulness, gentleness and self-control. It is just from one source, and there are still many other sources in the Bible" (Nuhamara, 2018). Based on the opinions of the experts above regarding the value of Christian character when it is adjusted to the nation's character education policies set by the government and still based on the Bible, the authors describe indicators of students with Christian character as follows:

First, the value of character concerning God. Faith in Christianity teaches that the existence of God is a Spirit that cannot be touched and seen directly. However, He can be recognized by His works. God's work is none other than His word itself. The Word of God in Ezekiel 36:27 says: "My Spirit I will give to dwell within you and I will make you live according to all My statutes and stick to My regulations and do them" (also compare verse 25 and verse 26; Ephesians 4:2-3, 5:1-2). However, the closeness of the relationship between humans (students) and God always experiences ups and downs. Humans tend to make mistakes and sins to separate themselves from God. However, because of God's loving nature, humans who have died because of sin are revived in Christ Jesus (Romans 6:6-11). Therefore, every Christian (student) must live in faith in Christ (Galatians 2:20). As an indicator of the Christian character of students who have faith, they have a close relationship with God, for example: diligent in praying, worshiping, like to read the Bible;

Second, the character value in oneself. We can find the value of character within ourselves in God's Word, written in 1 Peter 3:10-11, which reads: "Whoever wants to love life and wants to see good days, he must guard his tongue against evil and his lips from evil speech. -deceptive speech. He must shun evil and do good; seek peace and strive for it." Based on the text of God's word above, it can be found that indicators of Christian character students are honest, do not like to fight, take care of themselves, and so on;

Third, the value of character concerning others. In Christianity, it is said that God has the nature of the Most Merciful. Even God loved the world first, even though the world has fallen into the valley of sin. This form of love sends the word through the only begotten Son as a human, namely Jesus Christ (John 3:16). Love is one of the main teachings in Christianity (compare John 15:12,17; Galatians 6:9-10; Philippians 2:1-5). Therefore love is a student's Christian character concerning others. Galatians 5:22-23 reads: But the fruit of the Spirit is: love, joy, peace, patience, kindness, goodness, faithfulness, gentleness, self-control. There is no law against those things." So, indicators of Christian character students are loving, joyful, patient with others and others;

Fourth, the character value concerning the environment is caring for God's creation, including the natural environment. This is because indifference to the environment can lead to natural disasters that can claim victims, both property and lives and so on. God's command to protect the environment has been conveyed by God since the time of human creation. This is written in Genesis 2:8-25; Genesis 1:28, which reads thus: "God blessed them, then God said to them: fill the earth and subdue it, have dominion over the fish in the sea and the birds in the sky and over all the animals that creep on the

earth.". Based on the Word of God, the indicators of students having Christian character concerning the environment are: being diligent in picking up trash, cleaning the school environment, and so on.

Fifth, the value of character concerning nationality. The teachings of the Christian faith can be called very nationalist. In one verse in the Bible, it says: "Everyone must submit to the government that is above him, for there is no government that is not from God, and God establishes the governments that exist" (Romans 13:1). The attitude to submit and obey and do good to the government can also be found in 1 Peter 2:13, 16 and Titus 3:1. This Word of God invites students to uphold their sense of nationalism. As an indicator of students with Christian character concerning nationality, they participate in flag ceremony activities, follow applicable government regulations, etc.

Parental Example

In a family, parents are biological fathers and mothers who are considered old and need to be respected and have absolute authority from God to raise and educate their children responsibly (Anwar, 2003). Parents are responsible for shaping the character of children. Because parents are children's first teachers (Sarumpaet., 1995), Christian parents must realize that the family is the center of the formation of children's character (Harefa, 2016).

Parental example is principal in building and shaping children's character. By setting an example, forming a child's Christian character will be optimal. In general, parents are people who are considered old. In a family, parents are biological fathers and mothers who are considered old and need to be respected and whom absolute authority from God to raise and educate their children responsibly (Anwar, 2003) have. The basis of the word exemplary is things that can be imitated or emulated.

A parental example is an act or behavior that is good; then it should be imitated by students from what is done by parents in their duties as parents, both speech and actions that can be applied in everyday life (Suhono, 2019). Exemplary is a form of parenting that is a process of how to shape one's character in the family (Sundarsih, 2019).

The position and function of a family in human life are primary and fundamental. A family is a place for the formation of each member, especially children who are still under the guidance of their parents' responsibilities (Mulyono, 1993). The family is a trusted function for sharing the burden of problems, discussing the main issues, maturing the emotional side, and getting spiritual support (Mulyono, 1993). When children under pressure from the family, especially the child's parents, are more silent, the "silent culture" is characterized by the absence of dialogue and communication between family members (Mulyono, 1993). Parents' example can be felt by children when they try to treat their children fairly, correctly, and full of love (Christenson, 1994).

The basis for the obligation of parents to set an example for their children is clearly stated in Deuteronomy 6:6-7. The Israelites called this part of the book Shema Yisrael. Syema Yisrael's statement also has the goal that Israelis, especially parents, teach their children to know and love God from a young age. In this teaching delivered by Moses, God wants to teach about God to be the top priority. The emphasis on the word "Must.." in Deuteronomy 6:7 gives an emphasis that parents inevitably have to teach their children about God. Solomon also wrote in Proverbs that educating children cannot be ignored. Proverbs 22:6 says, "Educate your children in the way that is right for them so that even when they are old, they will not deviate from their way." In this case, parents are ordered to be educators. It can be understood that parental example can be seen from the role of parents as husband or wife and as parents responsible for nurturing, educating, and being priests for their children.

Parents' exemplary indicators

Indicators of good role models from parents that children can emulate are how parents talk and dress. They judge their behavior by examples from adults who have contributed to their lives (Kenny, 1991). Parents must also live by the example set by God, as it is written in the Bible: "For this, you were called because Christ also suffered for you and left an example for you, that you might follow in His footsteps" (1 Peter 2:21).

Bavery La Haye also cites Bible verses as guidelines for good parenting in his family, namely: "Do not act as if you want to rule over those entrusted to you, but be an example to the flock (1 Peter 5:3) (Haye, 2010). Another opinion says that "effective teaching of faith must first be expressed through action and example, then by words. Parental examples, daily experience, and parental participation in worship activities are the basic ingredients for introducing children to the concept of God (Haystead, n.d.).

The indicator of parental example, according to I Timothy 4:12 in this study is as follows. (1) Example in Word. Paul wanted Timothy to be an example for believers in words. The word in Greek "logos" has meaning, namely: speech, talk, preaching, word, sermon. (2) Exemplary in Conduct. In Greek, behavior is "anastrophe," a way of life, behavior, or attitude. This implies that the Word of God must control the life of every believer; in behavior, he must be patient, responsible, and with integrity. Parents do as they are told to children. (3) Example in Love. Love in the Greek language "agape" means true love, divine love, unconditional love, self-sacrificing love, and love that will not be shaken by circumstances, no matter how bad. (4) An Example of Faithfulness. Faithfulness in Greek is "pistis," which means trust, faith, and faithfulness, which denotes that you believe in God and be faithful to Him. In the original language, the words "Faith" and "Loyalty" have the same root word (pistis). In English, the word faithful is used, which means full of faith and is the same as faithful. (5) Example in Holiness. Chastity in Greek, "hagneia," refers to the purity of life without blemish, keeping the heart and mind pure and pure, keeping away from negative things. Children must be taught about holiness; they can be taught through words, such as not saying dirty words to friends or other people.

The Relationship between Parents' Exemplary and Student's Christian Character

Based on the explanation above, the relationship between students' parents and students' Christian character is as follows: Parents' example is very much needed at the stage of student development because students imitate the attitudes and behavior of people around them. With good attitudes and role models coupled with strengthening 'emotional bonding' between children and parents, efforts to infiltrate moral values and good character in children will be easier. Verkuyl further stated the following: If parents gamble, do not expect that children will not do it. If parents are drunk, do not expect that children will abstain from drinking. If parents are corrupt and extortionists, do not expect that children can be held accountable in financial terms. If parents never pray, leave their Bibles closed, never go to church, do not expect children to be able to pray, read the Bible, and attend church (Verkuyl, 1982). It can be understood that there is a relationship between parental example and children's character.

4. Conclusion

Christian character is a process. Deed forms innate, heart, soul, personality, character, behavior, personality, character, temperament, one's characteristics, temperament, character to apply good values in the form of action or behavior and has personality, an essential characteristic of intending to be a follower of Christ or a follower of Christians. Having Godly character (Father-Child), giving

character, not easily offended, non-violence, happy, friendly, disciplined, gender equality, national-minded, trustworthy, appreciative, responsible, fair, caring, sociable, and honest. The biblical perspective of Christian character is integrity, humility, love with all its characteristics, serving and helping, strong and true inwardly, closely related to Christ, having joy, holiness, peace, patience, perseverance, gentleness, self-control, not being greedy, not contentious, living in virtue, knowledge, and piety, mercy, faithfulness.

Values and indicators for students with Christian character: First, character values concerning God with indicators: diligence in praying, worshiping, likes to read the Bible; Second, self-character values with indicators: honesty, do not like to fight, taking care of themselves, and others; Third, character values concerning others with indicators: loving, joyful, patient with others and others; Fourth, character values concerning the environment with indicators: being diligent in picking up trash, cleaning the school environment, and others; Fifth, character values concerning nationality with indicators: participating in flag ceremony activities, following applicable government regulations, etc.

The example of parents towards children (students) is within the absolute authority of parents from God to raise and educate their children in a responsible manner which can be imitated or imitated from what is done, the words that are applied in the formation of children, guidance, dialogue, and communication between family members who can be felt by children fairly, correctly and full of love in the form of Syema Yisrael so that children know God and love God since childhood and make it a top priority that cannot be ignored. Parental examples can be seen from the role of parents as husband or wife and as parents responsible for nurturing, educating, and being priests for their children.

The indicator of exemplary parents towards children is the Greek word "logos," in the Greek language, "anastrophe" behavior; the example of Greek love is "agape," the example in Greek faithfulness is "pistis" and the example of holiness. Chastity in Greek "hagneia" refers to the purity of life. A good relationship between parents and students' Christian character is very much needed at the stage of student development because students imitate the good attitudes and behavior of people from their surroundings coupled with strengthening 'emotional bonding' between children and parents, efforts to infiltrate moral values and good character in children it will be easier to do. So it can be understood that a relationship exists between parental example and children's character.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank all parties including reviewers and journal editors who have helped us so that this article can be published in this journal.

References

- Antoni, H. S. (2010). *Pendidikan Kristiani Kontekstual*. BPK Gunung Mulia.
- Anwar, T. D. (2003). *Kamus Lengkap Bahasa Indonesia Terbaru* (1st ed.). Amelia.
- Brummelen, H. Van. (2006). *Berjalan Dengan Tuhan Di Dalam Kelas*. Universitas Pelita Harapan Press.
- Christenson, L. (1994). *Keluarga Kristen*. Buku Betania.
- G.I. Williamson, W. (2017). *Pengakuan Iman*. Momentum.
- Gill, D. W. (2000). *Becoming Good: Building Moral Character*. Downer Grove: Inter-Varsity Press.
- Gunawan, S. T. (2013). *Membangun dan Mengembangkan Karakter Kristen yang Kuat*. http://artikel.sabda.org/membangun_dan_mengembangkan_karakter_kristen_yang_kuat
- Harefa, O. (2016). *Keluarga Sebagai Pusat Pembentukan Rohani Anak*. Sekolah Tinggi Theologia Real Batam.
- Haye, B. La. (2010). *Memahami Temperamen Anak Anda*. Kalam Hidup.
- Haystead, W. (n.d.). *Mengenalkan God Kepada Anak*. In 1982. BPK Gunung Mulia.
- Indriswari, L., & Giawa, K. (2020). Pengaruh Pelaksanaan Pendidikan Agama Kristen Terhadap Karakter Anak. *EDUKASI: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Agama Dan Keagamaan*, 11(1).
- Jeti, L., Manan, Risman, K., & E. (2021). Application of Philosophy Values of Bhinci-Bhinciki Kuli in Early Childhood at Wolio Community. *Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v5i1.643>
- Kadarmanto, M. (2016). Mengkaji Revolusi Mental Dalam Perspektif Pendidikan. *A Journal of Language, Literature, Culture, and Education Polygot*, 7.
- Kadarwati, T. W. and S. (2013). *Higher Order Thinking Berbasis Pemecahan Masalah Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Berorientasi Pembentukan Karakter Siswa*. Cakrawala Pendidikan.
- Kemendiknas. (2010). *Pembinaan Pendidikan Karakter di Sekolah Menengah Pertama*. Kemendiknas.
- Kenny, J. K. & M. (1991). *Dari Bayi Sampai Dewasa*. BPK Gunung Mulia.
- Mulyono, Y. B. (1993). *Pendekatan Sosiologis, Psikologis, Teologis, Mengatasi Kenakalan Remaja* (2nd ed.). Yayasan Andi.
- Nahumara, D. (2018). Pengutamaan Dimensi Karakter dalam Pendidikan Agama Kristen. *Jurnal Jaffray*, 16(1).
- Sarumpaet, R. (1995). *Rahasia Mendidik Anak*. BPK Gunung Mulia.
- Sijabat, B. (1994). *Strategi Pendidikan Kristen*. Yayasan Andi.
- Suhono, F. U. (2019). Keteladanan Orangtua dan Guru dalam Pertumbuhan dan Perkembangan Anak Usia Dini. *Jurnal Elementtary*, 3(1).
- Sundarsih, S. (2019). Pentingnya Keteladanan Orangtua dalam Keluarga Sebagai Dasar dalam Pembentukan Karakter Masyarakat Jepang. *Jurnal Kiryoku*, 3(1).
- Suyanto, A. J. (2022). *Menerapkan Pendidikan Karakter di Sekolah*. Esensi.
- Tim-Kompas. (2020). Siswa SMP Tewas Berkelahi dengan Teman. *Kompas.Com*.
- Verkuyl, J. (1982). *Etika Kristen Seri Seksual*. BPK Gunung Mulia.
- Wibowo, A. (2017). *Pendidikan Karakter Usia Dini (Strategi Membangun Karakter di Usia Dini)*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- Zain, J. S. B. dan. (1996). *Kamus Umum Bahasa Indonesia*. Pustaka Sinar Harapan.